

AQUAWIND

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

D7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

AQUAWIND

Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy
and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin

Grant Agreement n°. 101077600

Co-funded by
the European Union

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author
1.0	28/11/2022	First version of the D&C plan submitted to the EC.	Teresa Gubern, Tamara Ventura, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello
2.0	05/12/2022	Table 3, fisheries updated	Idem

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	AquaWind	
Project Title	Innovative multi-use prototype combining offshore renewable energy and aquaculture in the Atlantic Basin	
Type of action	EMFAF-PJG EMFAF Project Grants	
Topic	EMFAF-2021-PIA-FLAGSHIP	
Project Start Date	01/09/2022	
Project Duration	36 months	
Work Package	WP7 Dissemination and Communication, RRI, Public engagement	
Deliverable	D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan	
Due Date	30/11/2022	
Submission Date	28/11/2022	
Dissemination Level ¹	PU	
Deliverable Responsible	Consulta Europa (CE)	
Version	1	
Author(s)	Teresa Gubern, Tamara Ventura, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello	CE
Reviewer(s)	Javier Roo, Rafael Ginés, Almudena Suárez, Gordon Dalton, Elba Bueno, Pedro Mayorga, Maria Ikhennicheu, Inês Machado, Alfred Mormeneo	GOBCAN ULPGC FCPCT PLOCAN CMC EnerOcean Innosea WAVEC CANEXMAR

¹ PU= Public, SEN = Sensitive, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

TABLE OF CONTENT

Executive summary	9
1. Context analysis.....	10
1.1. The project	10
1.2. The Consortium.....	10
1.3. AquaWind’s Dissemination and Communication Work package.....	11
2. Communication and dissemination principles	13
2.1. EC Rights and Obligations related to Results	13
2.2. Intellectual and property rights	14
3. Target groups	16
3.1. Identification	16
3.2. Communication channels	17
3.3. Co-creation of project key messages	18
3.4. Tailored communication, dissemination and engagement activities	19
4. Communication tools and guidelines	23
4.1. External and internal Communication	23
4.2. Project visual identity	23
4.3. Information leaflets, posters, and roll-up banner.....	24
4.4. Website	25
4.5. Social media	26
4.5.1. Social media plan.....	27
4.6. Newsletter	28
4.6.1. Customer Relationship Management and General Data Protection Regulation.....	28
4.6.2. Newsletter content and distribution	30
4.7. Press interviews	31

4.8.	Press release	32
4.8.1.	Approval process of press releases	32
4.9.	Videos	33
5.	Events and conferences.....	34
5.1.	Events organized by AquaWind	34
5.1.1.	Stakeholder engagement activities	34
5.1.2.	Training events	35
5.1.3.	Webinars.....	35
5.1.4.	International conference	35
5.2.	Assistance to other events.....	36
5.2.1.	Mapping of events.....	36
5.2.2.	National / EU events.....	37
6.	Press office	38
7.	Management of intellectual property rights.....	39
8.	Synergies and networking	40
8.1.	Objectives and presentations	40
8.2.	Targets	40
8.3.	Methodology.....	41
9.	Contingency plans	43
10.	Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities	48
10.1.	Monitoring of communication and dissemination activities	48
10.2.	Monitoring on partners' dissemination activities	48
10.3.	Evaluation of communication activities.....	50
11.	Progress on dissemination and communication activities	51
11.1.1.	Roll up	51

11.1.2.	Leaflet.....	52
11.1.3.	Website	53
11.1.4.	Social media	61
11.1.5.	Events.....	62

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1. AquaWind's logotype.	24
Figure 2. AquaWind's colours and typography.....	24
Figure 3. Roll-up.	51
Figure 4. Leaflet.	52
Figure 5. Website "Home".....	53
Figure 6. Website: About.....	54
Figure 7. Website: work packages.....	54
Figure 8. Website: Consortium.....	55
Figure 9. Networking tab.....	56
Figure 10. Website: Project description under "Project" tab.....	57
Figure 11. Website: Project tab: Results.	57
Figure 12. Website: gallery.....	58
Figure 13. Website: News & social media feed.	59
Figure 14. Website: AquaWind in the News.....	59
Figure 15. Website: Events.....	60
Figure 16. Website: Contact form.	61

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. AquaWind's consortium	11
Table 2. WP7 tasks' descriptions.....	12
Table 3. Target groups description.....	17
Table 4. Target groups communication details.....	18
Table 5. Tailored C&D, and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.	20
Table 6. Projects deliverables and their targeted dissemination groups.	20
Table 7. List of the partner's social media.....	27
Table 8. Provision calendar for newsletters' release.....	31
Table 9. List of possible projects to create synergies with.....	41
Table 10. Supporting tools for online photo exhibitions.....	43
Table 11. Supporting tools for online videos.....	43

Table 12. Supporting tools for online quiz events.....	44
Table 13. Supporting tools for creative competitions / social media challenges.....	44
Table 14. Supporting tools for creative online workshops.....	44
Table 15. Supporting tools for virtual open-door day/fair.....	45
Table 16. Supporting tools for virtual summits.....	45
Table 17. Supporting online tools for webinars.....	46
Table 18. Supporting tools for online podcasts.....	47
Table 19. Monitoring and evaluation activities.....	49
Table 20. Monitoring and evaluation indicators.....	50

ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
D	Deliverable
DM	Dissemination Manager
DoA	Description of the Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IM	IPR and innovation management
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
MT	Management Team
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the first deliverable from the 7th work package “Dissemination and Communication, RRI, Public engagement” of the AquaWind project. It consists of a comprehensive plan to guide the communication and dissemination activities of the project. This Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan outlines the core D&C activities during the 36-month duration of the project. This Plan will be internally updated upon needs.

This D&C Plan defines in detail all activities, tools needed and responsibilities of each partner. The D&C Plan will cover both internal and external communication and define:

- key communication messages to be shared and used by all project partners
- communication targets to be reached
- communication tools tailored to the specific needs of each target group
- calendar of activities
- monitoring and reporting of D&C activities

This first version of the D&C Plan includes general guidelines for the implementation of a variety of dissemination and communication activities, including publication of information on the project website, the use of social medias, the organization of first events and the production of first videos. It defines the actions to be taken, events to be attended as well as notions of the first stakeholders’ analysis for dissemination and communication purposes. In particular, the Plan presents the different categories of stakeholders to reach and to engage with and within the AquaWind project. Different communication channels are presented in the document to ensure the dissemination activities reach effectively each target group.

This Plan also presents the practical steps for the monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities under section 10 “Monitoring and evaluation of dissemination activities”.

1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1. THE PROJECT

The aim of AquaWind is to perform a demonstration test of a multi-use (MU) integrated and co-located solution. This would consist of joining an existing marine renewable energy production W2Power prototype with a newly developed innovative finfish aquaculture solution. The aquaculture prototype will include a tailor-made design fish cage with novel net materials, high level of digitalization and species diversification. Whereas the W2Power will consist of floating wind technology. This project performs, for the first-time, MU test trials joining marine energy production with live fish aquaculture in the Atlantic region. AquaWind joins efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholders' consortia including R&D centres, companies, a regional authority and a maritime cluster from three EU members states (FR, ES, PT) in the Atlantic basin.

In addition to that, AquaWind will involve a wide network of stakeholder throughout all the project phases to ensure social acceptance. The project will provide a route map for regulatory and legal issues that need to be addressed for real implementation of MU projects, taking advantages, and facilitating interaction with previous and ongoing EU funded projects. Additionally, AquaWind will demonstrate how the joint activity can be digitised to be remotely operated in the same maritime space with different fish species and how one activity might affect the other, before going one step further to becoming the new W2Power prototype in a commercial solution. Thus, AquaWind will provide real data to demonstrate the economic, environmental, and social sustainability of the MU proposal: providing a business model case and exploitation plan to evaluate the cost reduction of commissioning, maintenance and operation of the combined activity of the prototype. Also, it will provide real data of the monitoring campaign to evaluate the environmental impact in surrounding maritime space following the CO₂ footprint.

1.2. THE CONSORTIUM

AquaWind project is managed by a **consortium of 9 partners and 1 affiliated entity from 3 countries** (Spain, Portugal and France) ranging from universities and research institutes to governmental institutions and small enterprises (SMEs) and companies related to aquaculture and wind offshore energy. The consortium is listed on Table 1.

Table 1. AquaWind's consortium

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Acronym	Country
1	Agencia Canaria De Investigación Innovación y Sociedad De La Información	GOBCAN/ACIISI	ES
2	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation	CE	ES
3	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	ULPGC	ES
3.1	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la ULPGC	FCPCT	ES
4	Plataforma Oceánica de Canarias	PLOCAN	ES
5	Asociación Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	CMC	ES
6	EnerOcean S.L	EO	ES
7	INNOSEA	INNOSEA	FR
8	WAVEC/Offshore Renewables – Centro de Energía Offshore Associacao	WAVEC	PT
9	Canarias Explotaciones Marinas S.L	CANEXMAR	ES

1.3. AQUAWIND'S DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION WORK PACKAGE

The main objective of this **Work Package 7 (WP7)** is to disseminate information about the project to a wide audience, including researchers, academics, scientists and technicians, entrepreneurs, investors, policy makers and other public and private stakeholders such as fishermen and citizens. This WP is also responsible for carrying out communication activities to promote the visibility of the project itself. WP7 will create the tools and framework for effective project communication, awareness and capacity raising, peer exchange and dissemination of results.

WP7 will work in close synergy with WP1 and WP5. WP1 will be in charge of stakeholder planning (task 1.3) and stakeholder engagement activities (task 1.4), WP5 will foster and maximize the exploitation opportunities of the AquaWind multi-use solution.

This WP responds to all project objectives since it aims at disseminating and transferring the outputs and results of all AquaWind activities to its key stakeholders. The specific objectives of this WP are:

- To give visibility to the project and raise awareness among the public on the opportunities provided by multiuse solutions
- To support stakeholder engagement activities, trigger societal acceptance, engage stakeholders, and support the establishment of a local and European community supportive to use of RES and aquaculture and multi-use solutions
- To support knowledge transfer through scientific and non-scientific publications, organization of trainings events
- To connect with a wide network of EU projects, initiatives to exchange experience and promote R&I activities on multi-use
- To foster a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) approach as well as gender equality

Communication and dissemination activities in AquaWind will aim thus at ensuring visibility of the project but also at triggering effective interactions with stakeholders at the many project's interfaces.

This deliverable “D7.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan” is the key starting point for WP7 dissemination and communication activities. It will be considered as a living document, executed throughout the duration of the project and reviewed and internally updated upon needs and progression of the project activities.

Task 7.1 is the creation of the dissemination and communication strategy. The remaining tasks that are part of this D&C plan are:

Table 2. WP7 tasks' descriptions.

Nº	Task title.	Task description
7.2	Creation of D&C products and materials	This task deals with the production of several materials and tools including the project website, logo and corporate image, layout, posters and roll-ups as well as banners for social media, and three videos.
7.3	Organization of events, webinars, workshops, trainings	This task deals with the organization of different events formats, each of one targeting a specific type of stakeholders.
7.4	Synergies with other funded projects	This task deals with establishing relations with other funded projects to foster synergies in knowledge transfer and in exploitation of AquaWind.
7.5	Monitoring and evaluation of Dissemination and Communication activities	Reporting on D&C activities will be performed to measure efforts and results obtained and modify the D&C plan accordingly.
7.6	Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	Creation of a RRI plan for the project. To implement a yearly RRI audit of RRI practice using the MUSICA RRI Self-assessment toll RRI SAT. Final report at the end of the project.

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PRINCIPLES

This paragraph presents a set of five principles upon which the AquaWind Dissemination Plan has been built:

- **Adaptability.** Given the scope of the project and the specific themes involved, the communication and dissemination activities need to be adaptable to the project's various research themes and stakeholder communities and project progress. For example, specific channels are to be used to reach particular target groups, and dissemination materials may have to be tailored to the needs of different end users. The targets groups will be specified in section 3 Target groups.
- **Flexibility.** Communication needs to be flexible and open to create a responsive framework to changing needs and challenges.
- **Tailoring of messages/usage of appropriate language.** AquaWind needs to be able to speak to a variety of actors and stakeholders with different background and objectives in mind. To achieve this, the project must formulate key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, and expressed in appropriate language (specialised, technical communication vs. plain, jargon-free communication using laymen's language).
- **Exploitation of synergies.** To maximize impact and efficiency of exploitation an extensive network of external collaborations of project partners will be used, and opportunities sought to join and contribute to existing networks and platforms which have relevant remits.
- **Gender sensitive and inclusive communication.** Certain words and images we use to communicate must be considered carefully since they can perpetuate images of socially prescribed gender roles and behaviours. AquaWind will adopt a non- hierarchical and nonpatronizing style, to promote gender-sensitive communication, identify gender stereotypes and use a fair and balanced representation of women and men in communication.

2.1. EC RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS RELATED TO RESULTS

Dissemination of results is a contractual obligation for projects funded under the EMFAF programme. The partners must, therefore, conduct various dissemination activities through different means including electronic tools such as project websites, e-publications, information platforms, and promotional material such as leaflets, press releases, posters, as well as various events including stakeholder workshops, thematic meetings, and conferences at national and European level. At the same time, however, dissemination activities shall be compatible with the protection of intellectual property rights, confidentiality obligations and the legitimate interests of the owner(s) of the foreground, as stated in the Grant Agreement.

The granting authority has the right to use non-sensitive information relating to the action and materials and documents received from the beneficiaries on a royalty-free basis. More information regarding this can be found at Article 16 the [Annotated Model Grant Agreement](#) or at AquaWind's own Grant Agreement (GA).

To implement dissemination and exploitation activities effectively, it is thus essential to have a good understanding of the definitions of the respective terms and concepts within the context of EMFAF projects. Project partners are therefore encouraged to consult the following key documents and online sources for the definition of various terms and description of various procedures and processes as well as the respective roles and responsibilities of each party.

- AquaWind's GA including Annex 1 – Description of the Action (DoA), in particular description of WP7; and Terms and Conditions of the Grant Agreement, in particular chapter 4 Grant Implementation, section 2 Rules for carrying out the action, articles 16 & 17.
- AquaWind's Consortium Agreement (CA), in particular section 8 (Results), section 9 (Access Rights), and section 10 (Non-disclosure of Information).

Furthermore, project's materials must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Co-funded by the European Union

The emblem can be found in the following [LINK](#). It must remain distinct and separate. It cannot be modified by adding other visuals. When displayed with other logos, it must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

Any relevant communication or dissemination activity related to the action must indicate the following disclaimer:

“Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Partners should keep track of all their dissemination and exploitation activities and report to WP7 Leader: Consulta Europa (CE). The WP leader will then report the statistics to the EC at the reporting stages. CE is required to report any publication and dissemination activities on the Grant Management System of the EU Funding and Tenders Portal.

2.2. INTELLECTUAL AND PROPERTY RIGHTS

The Consortium acknowledges the importance of IPR and innovation management (IM) for results developed within the AquaWind project. Dedicated tasks have therefore been included in WP5 T5.2 to actively monitor outputs in terms of innovation potential, implementation of IPR protection measures, or

open innovation models. The innovation management (led by PLOCAN) will be fully integrated in the Exploitation Plan (EP- WP5 - D5.2). The EP will also draft business plans for the market penetration of the outputs. The CA will detail all aspects concerning IPR-related matters. The IM will play a pivotal role in ensuring an effective and end-user driven innovation management. This will include the management of partners' Background used for the project implementation, as well as the protection and regulation of generated Foreground.

During the project implementation, the GA, with the supervision and strong collaboration of the IM, will monitor the produced results and identify any specific issue that requires prior agreement among partners. The GA will also undertake any needed measure to identify results that are suitable for commercial exploitation and identify proper exploitation strategies to be proposed to the IM. Decisions related to IPR issues will be taken by the GA. The harmonization and integration of data and indicators will be a key functional activity to enable the application of methods and tools and will require an appropriate Data Management Plan (DMP, under the leadership of GOBCAN) to be periodically refined and completed in order to establish data-sharing policies and regulate access rights for the databases, coherently with the CA rules and the DMP.

3. TARGET GROUPS

3.1. IDENTIFICATION

One of AquaWind's objectives is the implementation of an inclusive process, by engaging stakeholders at regional, national, and European level, prioritising public administrations, academia, business sector comprising the supply chain at local level, as well as social agents such as business associations, fishermen and civil society.

During the project, a **stakeholder's identification** will be carried out through different tasks, mainly at WP1 and WP5. For this purpose, a mapping of stakeholders (task 1.3) of the quadruple helix will be carried out previously to ensure a wide representation of these stakeholders as target groups in the communication and dissemination of the project. This mapping will consist of a **technical survey** that will be launched to collect information from the stakeholders, and to focus the activities that will be part of the stakeholder engagement plan (task 1.4) such as interviews, focus groups, technical workshops, and matchmaking actions.

Initially, a set of target groups have been identified (Table 3) that might be adjusted after the activities under WP1.

A stakeholders' analysis at the regional, national and international with a special focus at EU level is being performed at the moment on WP1 Setting legal and social conditions, task 1.3 "Planning stakeholder engagement". The first deliverable regarding this task "D1.3 Stakeholder Engagement Plan" will be submitted at M6, February 2023. Once submitted, this and other sections of this deliverable will be updated according to the Stakeholder's analysis.

Table 3. Target groups description.

Target group	Description
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	Science stakeholders include a diverse network of actors managing, coordinating, or conducting scientific research related to marine activities. This group includes the research community, science managers as well students and Phd scientists. The science category includes actors at local, national, intergovernmental, and European levels as well as representatives of other EU projects.
Industry Representatives, Investors	This category includes representatives of the fishery sector, aquaculture, renewable energy but also maritime transport. In particular companies willing to commercialise the products and services developed in the demo work packages will require robust exploitation plans, risk and benefit assessments, which will be produced under WP5. They will also benefit from the networking opportunities and communication activities offered under WP7.
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations)	This category includes both citizens and organizations which operate in the marine field and are affected by marine related activities and citizens who have no specific knowledge of MUP and are not affected by marine activities in their everyday life. The general public will receive awareness-raising materials to trigger their interest, improve their literacy on renewable energy and aquaculture needs and their relevance for climate change mitigation and food production. In addressing the general public, citizen science activities will be promoted as for the first group, environmental organizations, local action groups, and other type of associations will be reached to provide them with comprehensive information on AquaWind solutions and to foster social acceptance.
Fisheries communities	The fisheries communities are part of the societal actors but are also a key target group on its own. Due to the nature of the project, combining not only off shore wind energy that might interfere with fisheries space and the fishes itself but with the aquaculture part that might pose a threat to the artisanal ways of fishing in the islands. For this reason, most of the activities for WP1, task 1.3 and task 1.4 consider this target group in specific. Efforts will be made to understand their conception and opinion on AquaWind and on organising workshops and webinars to inform about the project, their job prospects and circumstances that will not damage this sector but increase their activity in any case. As understood by some partners, and as it has happened already at PLANASER 2.0 , the fisheries communities will and have been asked for their help, which will in turn benefit them as well. The approach to the fishing community will be carried out through the Fisheries Local Action Groups (FLAGs). FLAGs are entities with their own local development strategies, which in specific fishing and aquaculture areas bring together companies, public entities, third sector and research entities to implement the aforementioned strategies.
Policy and decision-makers	They will require short and concise recommendations and visual documentation facilitating the understanding of how MUP can impact a broader policy sector and how policy can support or hamper the installations of MUPs. Policymakers at regional, national and EU level will be targeted. At EU level several Directorates-General will be reached (RTD, CLIMA, ENER, ENV, MARE), the JRC, European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency; the European Parliament (intergroups, committees, MEPs), international Ocean governance initiatives, OECD Ocean Economy working group.

3.2. COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

On Table 4 the communication channels and type of information to be shared with each stakeholder is defined:

Table 4. Target groups communication details.

Target group	Communication channels	Type of information
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project results 	
Industry Representatives, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Business/exploitation plan 	
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + Fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project impact assessment 	
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advantages of the prototype 	

These groups might change depending on the stakeholder's identification carried out at the beginning of the project.

3.3. CO-CREATION OF PROJECT KEY MESSAGES

The aim of AquaWind is to perform in Canary Islands a demonstration test of a multi-use integrated solution joining an existing marine renewal energy production W2Power prototype based on floating wind technology with an innovative aquaculture solution including a tailor-made design fish cage with novel net materials, high level of digitalization and species diversification. The AquaWind solution will be designed and tested following a multi-stakeholder and circular approach to ensure social acceptance, optimal resource use and the lowest environmental impact possible. This will also support the development of business case supporting sustainability and replication initiatives. Therefore, the pillars of the project are:

- To demonstrate the feasibility of the multi-use integrated solution
- To perform a multi-stakeholder and circular approach for ensuring social acceptance
- To ensure the lowest environmental impact possible

- To develop business cases in relation to the multi-use solution

To achieve this, AquaWind has four specific objectives:

- To build a framework and develop specific solutions for integrated planning multiuse
- To ensure uptake, sustainability, and continuation of AquaWind pilot
- To demonstrate at pilot scale the feasibility of multi-use of offshore renewable energy prototype for a more sustainable aquaculture production and better use of marine space
- Demonstrate neutral or positive environmental and social impacts for the multi-use offshore renewable energy solution.

In order to communicate the pillars to stakeholders properly, a set of key messages determined by the project's partners must be created. To define these key messages a process of co-creation will be developed within the Consortium. The co-creation process will be carried at the SCs with a debate with the partners to define a set of strategic lines and key messages that will help to communicate the results of AquaWind. CE will present a set of various key messages that will be discussed and voted no later than Month 6: February 2023.

3.4. TAILORED COMMUNICATION, DISSEMINATION AND ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

An effective strategy of D&C should adapt its key messages to each type of audience/stakeholder targeted in order to achieve the maximum impact and engagement. At the same time, each project outputs should be appropriately channelled to achieve their highest exploitation levels.

The Table 5 tailors the D&C and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder. **Error! Reference source not found.** relates the project deliverables that will be disseminated publicly to each targeted audience.

Table 5. Tailored C&D, and engagement activities to each type of stakeholder.

Type of stakeholders	C&D activities	Engagement activities
Research community (researchers, PhD students)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshops/focus groups 	
Industry Representative, Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conferences 	
Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Focus groups 	
Policy and decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop/roundtables 	

Table 6. Projects deliverables and their targeted dissemination groups.

WP	Nº	Deliverable	Date	Target audience	
1	D1.1	Inventory of legal permissions, permits and consents	Feb 24	Project partners (not for dissemination)	
	D1.2	H&S Strategy and Plan	Aug 23		
	D1.3	Stakeholder Engagement Plan	Feb 23	Research community (researchers, PhD students)	
	D1.4	Recommendations for successful stakeholder involvement in MU platforms	Aug 25		
	D1.5	Circular approach model	Feb 24		
	D1.6	Progress Report ver.1, 2, 3 &4	Feb 23	Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + Fisheries	
	D1.7		Aug 23		
	D1.8		Aug 24		
	D1.9		Feb 25		
	D1.10	Policy Feedback report ver.1 & ver.2	Feb 24	Policy and decision makers	
D1.11	Aug 25				
2	D2.1	Detailed design specifications	Aug 23		Project partners (not for dissemination)
	D2.2	Drawings and designs for construction and logistics	Nov 23		
	D2.3	Design specifications of ICT and electrical for AquaWind	Feb 24		
	D2.4	Prototype upgraded for AquaWind trials, monitoring and supervision systems	Feb 24		
3	D3.1	Cage and net designs, set up and tested report	Aug 23		Project partners (not for dissemination)
	D3.2	Silo, autonomous feeder, sensors, and cameras, set up and remote monitoring test report	Nov 23		
	D3.3	Results of First live fish test with model fish at harbourside	Feb 24		
4	D4.1	W2Power Upgraded: Mooring	Aug 25		Project partners (not for dissemination)
	D4.2	Results of First offshore live fish test with model fish	Aug 25	Research community (researchers, PhD students)	
	D4.3	Results of Second offshore live fish test with novel fish.	Aug 25	Industry Representative, Investors	
	D4.4	Environmental impact assessment	Aug 25	Research community (researchers, PhD students) Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + fisheries Policy and decision makers	
5	D5.1	Knowledge and IP plan for consortium technologies ver.1 & ver.2	Aug 23	Research community (researchers, PhD students)	
	D5.5		Feb 24		
	D5.2	Sustainable business exploitation and job plan prospects	Aug 25	Industry Representative, Investors	
	D5.3	Partnerships and Spinout company	Jul 25	Policy and decision makers	
D5.4	Recommendations and policy brief for policy makers on multi- use	Jul 25			
6	D6.1	CA and Management Plan	Oct 22		

7	D6.2	Quality assurance Plan	Feb 23	Project partners (not for dissemination)
	D6.3	Risk management Plan	Aug 24	
	D6.4	Data management plan	Feb 23	
	D6.5	Report on adoption of Gender Equality and Diversity Principles	Aug 25	
	D7.1	D&C Plan	Nov 22	Research community (researchers, PhD students)
	D7.2	Videos produced ver.1, 2 & 3	Aug 23	
	D7.3		Aug 24	
	D7.4		Aug 25	Industry Representative, Investors
	D7.5	Report on D&C activities ver. 1 ver.2 ver.3	Aug 23	Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + fisheries
	D7.6		Aug 24	
D7.7	Aug 25			
D7.8	RRI project report	Aug 25	Policy and decision makers	
D7.9	Project Factsheet	Jan 23	Research community (researchers, PhD students)	
			Industry Representative, Investors	
			Societal Actors (citizens, public, civil society organisations) + fisheries	
			Policy and decision makers	

4. COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND GUIDELINES

To standardize communication and dissemination activities several communication tools and materials have been developed. This section will collect them and guide project partners on how to implement them.

4.1. EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

External communication activities will aim at delivering clear messages to the project stakeholders through a set of targeted communication tools and make a strong and impactful contribution to the project's high-level objectives of promoting installation of multi-use platforms combining renewable energy solutions with other marine activities. AquaWind will target representatives of the Quadruple Helix Model recognizing four major actors in the innovation system: **science, policy, industry, and society**. Even if some stakeholders belong to several categories an initial identification and classification will be done to define the best communication channels and tools for each category. All four Quadruple Helix categories are equally crucial for the AquaWind long-term success.

The **internal communication** needed for the correct dissemination and communication of the project will include a set of various internal communication activities:

- An internal shared folder will contain **all project details and documents** related to WP7. This can be found under the folder [3.Work Packages > WP7 D&C](#).
- Mailing lists will be created allowing easy contact with work package leaders, SC, and other external stakeholders groups
- Zoom will be the virtual meeting platform
- Friday email newsletter, sent weekly to the consortium when needed to highlight vital project development to the partnership

4.2. PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

AquaWind has developed a strong and consistent visual identity for an efficient dissemination of the results of the project. The first and central element to develop in order to have a consistent visual identity is the logo and the main colours and style that will be used throughout the project duration not only in D&C materials but in all documents of the project, thus defining the project's identity and ensure recognisability.

The logo in Figure 1 was developed by the WP leader with the feedback and suggestions of all partners. After several trials and options, the logo was chosen in a survey by the Consortium. To develop the logo, the two main elements of the multi-use solution: Aquaculture and Off-shore wind energy were given special importance being represented by the windmills and the fish.

Another element of special importance is the Circular economy which is represented by the circle closing the design. It represents AquaWind's objective to work towards the EU objective of a more sustainable,

just and circular economy in both the Aquaculture and the energetic sector. This project tackles all these problems and thus Circular Economy becomes the motor behind the prototype.

Figure 1. AquaWind's logotype.

Código HEX

#00a4a8	#004f7d
#3dc0e8	#edb400

Main typography

Myriad Pro Regular AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Condensed Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Light AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Semibold AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Semibold Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Bold Condensed AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Bold AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Bold Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
 Myriad Pro Bold Condensed Italic AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

Secondary typography

Calibri

Designer: Luc(as) De Groot

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz

1234567890~!@#\$%^&*(){[]}'"?`

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog.

Figure 2. AquaWind's colours and typography

4.3. INFORMATION LEAFLETS, POSTERS, AND ROLL-UP BANNER

To promote the main ideas of this project, a **leaflet** will be used. A template will be developed in the format of a booklet as key promotional material. The leaflet will be in a standard A4 size, folded in 2. This

booklet will provide information on what are the challenges facing the project, what are the objectives it intends to achieve and what are the work packages that constitute the work plan. It will also briefly explain what the vision of the project is and include the logos of the 10 members of the consortium (9 partners and 1 affiliated entity). It will be used and disseminated by the partners during relevant events and meetings (each partner being responsible for printing the leaflets). The electronic version of the leaflet is available on the website in a pdf format for downloading.

A standardised **roll-up** will be developed, the measures will be 85 cm x 200cm. This roll-up design will be adapted to create different printed versions such as a photocall roll-up with longer dimensions. The roll-up will be made available to be used by every partner to assist any on-site event. In addition to the printed version of the roll-up, there is going to be editions. This roll-up design will be adapted and will be used digitally to promote the project on different websites, platforms, digital newspapers and social media channels. The roll-up can be digitally downloaded from the website.

Project posters, postcards, and other relevant promotional material to be used in dissemination activities will be produced within this task. These materials will be created to draw the attention of the audience to the AquaWind project during different events.

4.4. WEBSITE

The AquaWind website will be created and developed in the first months of the project and filled out with all relevant information about the project and the consortium.

The website's structure is as follows:

- 🌐 Home. The first tab presents the visual identity, the name of the project and a brief description.
 - It also shows the Newsletter box to subscribe to the newsletter.
- 🌐 About. In the second tab there will be the main information regarding the project:
 - Work packages. Inside the project tab you can find all Work packages explained with pictures and results updates
 - Consortium. The third tab will consist of information regarding each partner (description, a map with locations of the partners, and so on).
 - Networking / Other sister projects. This tab under "About" will consist of useful information regarding other sister projects and other resources.
- 🌐 Project. In the third tab there will be information more specific of the project:
 - A full description of what is AquaWind and its objectives.
 - Results. The results are the most important part of the website, where the work of AquaWind is shown. First, dissemination and communication materials will be shared. Later, when Deliverables are submitted and approved, those that are meant to be public will also be shared here.
 - Gallery. This tab under "Project" is where all images and videos will be shared.
- 🌐 News. The fourth tab will consist of the news and social media feed, latest project news as well as news from other relevant projects, initiatives, and organizations in the field:
 - AquaWind News. This section will consist of news on AquaWind events and results.

- Social media feed. There will be a section to the right of the news solely on social media, showing the last tweets and posts.
- In the lower part of the page there will be a section called “AquaWind in the news”. This section will show what other media is saying about the project.
- 🌐 Events. The last section will show the events. This will be an agenda of AquaWind’s events and other events from relevant projects, initiatives, and organizations in the field:
- 🌐 Contact. Finally, the last tab will contain a contact section with an online form to be filled in. Also, this section will provide contact information and a legal warning to let users know how their data is used in case they decide to provide it (also by subscribing to the newsletter).

The website is accessible at the following address: <https://aquawind.eu/>. The website has been developed in English to be accessible to any kind of international and EU stakeholders. Its purpose is to act as “vitrine” of the project and to get in touch with interested parties since the very beginning of the project.

The website, as other D&C material will be a living space, that will be maintained, updated and further developed throughout the project to be as active and attractive as possible. It is for this reason that the website includes a section where to read regular news articles that will be posted and another section with all social media platforms integrated. **All project partners will provide information for the publication of news on the website to CE.**

4.5. SOCIAL MEDIA

For communication purposes a set of social media accounts will be developed, each targeting different audiences. The social media will be set up to promote Account via trending hashtags, live tweeting from high profile events.

AquaWind can be followed on Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn:

- 🌐 The [Facebook](#) page where all project partners and individuals can follow the page and check the news and updates of the project.
- 🌐 The [Instagram](#) account to share images of the events, keep posted on a more frequent basis than other social media, engage followers with activities and questionnaires and share information.
- 🌐 The [Twitter](#) account is used to share news links and keep people interested in the news of the project. It also works to get updates from other projects and actors valuable in AquaWind’s field.
- 🌐 The [LinkedIn](#) profile is a more professional account to engage partners, researchers and key actors of Aquaculture and offshore energy generation.
- 🌐 The [YouTube](#) account has also been created that will served as an audiovisual repository of all the content that is produced, videos of events, promotional videos, interviews, etc.

All these accounts have been created and will be updated regularly during the duration of the project with information on project results, partners, events organized, interviews, other relevant project’s events, results and information.

To share information and content with other partners, the following table has been created as a database, with all the addresses of the partners' social networks. This will help to make a coordinated and better online presence of the project through the posts shared between the entire consortium.

4.5.1. SOCIAL MEDIA PLAN

A social media plan will be developed according to the tasks and/or activities performed under every work package of the project. In addition to this, content will also be published related to the fields of aquaculture, renewable energies, blue economy, other sister projects, and so on. Mainly two lines of posts will regularly be published:

- Activities performed (Project results and updates)
- General Content (events, news, and other sister projects)

The social media plan will include specific campaigns according to vital milestones of the project.

Whenever possible, social media releases from the official accounts of the project will tag and make reference to the partners' own medial channels, which will act as multipliers of AquaWind news and posts. Social media accounts of the project partners are the following:

Table 7. List of the partner's social media.

Partner	Facebook	Twitter	Instagram	Linkedin	Youtube/vimeo
GOBCAN ACIISI	@ACIISI	@agenciaiisi	@aciisi	Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Informaciónhttps://www.linkedin.com/company/consulta-europa/	ACIISI Gobierno de Canarias
CE	@Consulta Europa	@Consulta_Europa	@consulta_europa	Consulta Europa	Consulta Europa
ULPGC	@ULPGC	@ULPGC	@ulpgc_para_tu	Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	Universidad ULPGC
FCPCT	@fcpctulpgc	@pctulpgc	@fcpct	Fundación Canaria Parque Científico Tecnológico de la Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	FCPCT ULPGC
PLOCAN	@plocan	@plocan	@laplocan	@plocan	@plocanplataforma

CMC	@ClusterMaritimoCanarias	@CMaritimoC	@clustermaritimocanarias	Cluster Marítimo de Canarias	Clúster Marítimo de Canarias
EO		@EnerOcean		@enerocean-s.l.	EnerOcean S.L
INNOSEA				@innosea	
WAVEC	@WavEC.Offshore.Renewables	@WavecOfficial		@wavecoffshorerenewables	WAVEC Offshore Renewables
CANEXMAR	@gestionderecursosmarinos				

4.6. NEWSLETTER

The newsletter is a valuable tool to share relevant and valuable information with AquaWind’s network of all different stakeholders. The newsletter will give the WP7 leader, CE, direct access to the project audience’s inbox, allowing CE to share engaging content, share results, events, foster synergies and drive traffic to AquaWind’s website. Additionally, the newsletter is easy to measure, which will mean that the progress can be easily measured, and adjustments can be made to increase interest.

4.6.1. CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT AND GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION

To register for the newsletter, stakeholders could use a subscription box found on the website, in the news section. The newsletter will be sent to all registered people by email through a dedicated Customer Relationship Management software, such as Mailchimp, Hubspot or Wordpress plug-in, which complies with the European Union General Data Protection Regulation by:

- Appointing a data protection officer to oversee our compliance programme.
- Continually reviewing security measures to ensure that all collected and processed personal data is adequately protected.
- Ensuring that the platform Global Privacy Statement clearly explains Mailchimp's, Hubspot's or WordPress commitment to the GDPR, is transparent about how personal data is used, and informs users about how they can exercise their rights in relation to the data.
- Incorporating EU standard contractual clauses into the Data Processing Addendum (DPA), which is part of the Standard Terms of Use and applies to customer data protected by EU law.
- Providing customers with GDPR-ready terms in the Data Processing Addendum and update contracts with third-party providers to ensure they are GDPR-compliant.

- Maintaining formal processes dedicated to data subjects' rights to ensure compliance with the user's requests.
- Responding to and comply with data subjects' rights requests in accordance with obligations as data controllers.
- Conducting data protection impact assessments to identify and minimise any risks that may arise from data processing activities.
- Keeping accurate records of processing activities, both as processors and controllers of personal data.
- Paying close attention to regulatory guidelines regarding GDPR compliance and making necessary changes to the features of the products and contracts.
- Relying on the EU-US/Switzerland-US privacy protection frameworks. EU-US/Switzerland-US privacy protection frameworks. Therefore, continuously protecting data from the EEA, UK and Switzerland in accordance with the Privacy Shield Principles. You can view Mailchimp Privacy Shield certification [here](#).

ABOUT CONSENT

Subscription to the newsletter is voluntary and the opt-out link will be visible in every issue. AquaWind's newsletter database must have a legal basis, such as consent, to process the personal data of an EU resident. Thus, our database relies on voluntary, specific, informed and unambiguous consent. In order to verify that we have obtained proper consent, a written record specifies when and how someone has agreed to allow you to process their personal data. Consent must also be unambiguous and require clear affirmative action. This means, using clear language and dispensing with pre-ticked consent boxes.

ABOUT INDIVIDUAL RIGHTS

The GDPR also describes the rights of individuals regarding their personal data. EU citizens have the right to request information about how you use their personal data and can ask about certain things with that data. To be prepared to respond to these requests, a Data Protection Officer has been appointed. Individuals have the right to request that their personal data be corrected, made available, prohibited for certain uses, or deleted altogether. This information is explained through the legal warning on the project website.

LEGAL WARNING

By subscribing to the AquaWind newsletter and registering to meetings or events, you will send us your e-mail (which is compulsory) and other information which is not compulsory, and we wish to inform you beforehand how it will be used.

Therefore, in compliance with the GDPR, we inform you that Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation, as partner in charge of the AquaWind's communication and dissemination activities, will process your data lawfully and fairly, only where necessary, using paper and electronic means, adopting adequate technical and organisational security measures, only for the purpose of sending you the newsletter as well as specific announcements of project activities (invitation to events, workshops, etc.) and to provide

statistics on the overall number of users registered, the type of organizations reached and the countries of belonging of the organizations.

The invitation to subscribe will be advertised on the project website and on the social media channels. All the partners of the consortium will be encouraged to invite a selected list of international and local stakeholders to subscribe. Other possible ways to promote the newsletter are:

- Promoting the opt-in link on Facebook and Instagram.
- Promoting the newsletter among the participants of AquaWind's events.
- Social media campaigns and subscription option in every registration form.
- Designed banners to be published on different websites incl. partners' websites and other digital means.

4.6.2. NEWSLETTER CONTENT AND DISTRIBUTION

The newsletter will be produced twice a year containing information on the project's achievements and initiatives and shared with the consortium and external subscribers. The newsletters will be in English. The Consortium will check if it is feasible to translate it to the other languages of the project partners (Spanish, French and Portuguese) with their help.

The newsletter design is developed according to the visual identity and is available in HTML and PDF format. To create each newsletter draft, partners are asked to participate by providing news and reports on their activities within the framework of the project, but also the main results, upcoming events, and other relevant activities. Partners are requested to send their contributions **one month** in advance to the release of the newsletter. The table below presents the time schedule of each newsletter, main contents, and schedule for contributions to be sent by project partners.

Table 8. Provision calendar for newsletters' release.

Nº	Main contents	Contribution by partners	Release of newsletter
1	AquaWind in the media	2 nd January 2023	15 th Jan 2023
2	Future events	1 st July 2023	15 th July 2023
3	Future events	1 st Jan 2024	15 th Jan 2024
4	Future events	1 st July 2024	15 th July 2024
5	Future events	1 st Jan 2025	15 th Jan 2025
6	Conclusions from final conference	1 st July 2025	15 th July 2025

4.7. PRESS INTERVIEWS

Press interviews are crucial to the D&C of the project. CE will continuously made press interviews with the help of the partners. These press interviews will be organised to recollect information as well as updating the project's dissemination products. At the same time, information from the press interviews will be used for the creation of press releases.

These press interviews will also help in designing communication products from what each partner is doing (information for the website, to update and share on social media, to update each WPs result, and so on.

Press interviews format:

- Phone call. to ask for **quotes** for strategic communications, web, and social media, to share for the radio and/or podcasts.

- Video. Small video pills for social media and YouTube. It can also be shared to TV and other media.

Not only CE will do all interviews, but there will also be a proactive interest from all partners to contact media sources to give interviews.

Interviews will be organised and given priority according to the Gantt chart most critical tasks, results, and events. These events can be the Kick-off meeting, conferences participations and the Final conference.

AquaWind will prepare at least 3 press interviews per year, to end the project with at least a minimum of 9 press interviews. AquaWind WP7 leader, CE, will work with the media departments within the consortium to exploit existing contacts.

4.8. PRESS RELEASE

There will be at least **9 press releases** related to the events or crucial announcement from AquaWind such as the Kick-Off meeting or the “Offshore wind energy day in Canary Islands”. These press releases will be mainly created by CE.

Press releases are made jointly with the partners. CE will create them for AquaWind key events and milestones and share with the Consortium for their communication responsible to adapt them.

Furthermore, each partner should get in touch when they are releasing a press release related to any of the actions planned in the project or, in general, with AquaWind. CE will then adapt it and share it with the SC again to ensure greater dissemination. Also, it is essential to share press releases in advance so the SC can check them before the release.

4.8.1. APPROVAL PROCESS OF PRESS RELEASES

At AquaWind it is essential to prepare the press releases in advance and share them with the Consortium for a check before sharing them with the media. For this reason, and the process for approval of press releases is the following:

- The press releases will be ready by the CE team **two weeks in advance** to the event or announcement date.
- It will be then **shared to the Consortium** for their review so they can send any feedback or changes desired to CE.
- The **final version** will be sent **one week before** the event to each partner’s press services to adapt it and share it on the day.

When the press release is created by another partner:

- The press releases will be shared with the SC and the SC will have **one week** to review and give feedback. Past that date, the partner is allowed to share the press release.

It is vital to show consistency in the D&C of AquaWind's results. Thus, the partners' press office should check that the style agreed by the Consortium is thoroughly followed. An example of this can be to always write **W2Power** instead of Wind2Power for the prototype or **AquaWind** instead of AQUAWIND.

4.9. VIDEOS

Throughout the project, in order to express the objectives of AquaWind in a clearer and more visual way, and reach a greater number of people, a series of videos will be produced. They will be produced to help raise public awareness of the **potential of multi-use platforms, renewable energy production, and aquaculture possibilities**. They will explain the importance of the EU support to this type of initiatives and bring about the main AquaWind messages outlined. Other videos will focus on demonstrating the technology of the multiuse platform in practice. Some videos will be more focused on image and with few and not sophisticated scripts while others will rather take the form of storytelling, involving representatives of the quadruple helix in addition to staff from project partners.

These videos will be produced in the following way:

- A first **animation video** at the beginning of the project to inform about the objectives and vision of it.
- A **demonstration video** of the technological and operational aspects of the AquaWind solution.
- A **storytelling video** involving staff from the project and other stakeholders involved in the project activities.

The videos will be produced in English with subtitles in the three languages of the Consortium (Spanish, Portuguese, French). These videos will be uploaded to AquaWind's YouTube channel and distributed across partners' websites and other websites such as CORDIS YouTube Channel or Science&Innovation YouTube channel.

5. EVENTS AND CONFERENCES

5.1. EVENTS ORGANIZED BY AQUAWIND

Different type of events has been planned, each type targeting specific groups and aimed at achieving specific objectives. These events will be held by different members of the partnership in their countries of origin while international conferences might be organized in Brussels or at other strategic locations (for instance in conjunction with other events).

Moreover, CE will provide **guidelines** and checklists to support project partners in the organization of the conferences and other dissemination events with stakeholders. Guidelines will cover different tasks related with the preparation, carrying out and evaluation of each event. Also, CE will ensure that the conferences will be distributed across the project duration and where possible that synergies and exchanges among different events will be sought.

Particular attention will be given to monitoring gender in the project events organized. The evaluation reports of each event will include the monitoring on the number of women participants.

5.1.1. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT ACTIVITIES

Based on the stakeholder engagement plan from WP1, and in conjunction with WP7, a set of diverse activities will be organized tailored to each type of organization, including interviews, focus groups, workshops, matchmaking activities. etc.

These activities will include, among others:

- Presentations & networking at relevant local / regional / national events
- Dedicated workshops for a focused engagement with specific target groups (industry and civil society)
- Citizen science initiatives in collaboration with the ULPGC and ACIISI/GOBCAN
- Presentations at schools on multi-use solutions to raise awareness of children and their families
- Interviews
- Focus groups
- Technical workshops
- Policy making events

In coordination with WP7 frameworks and guidelines, Tasks 1.3 and 1.4 will define and implement a practical plan for stakeholders' engagement activities. Such activities will be conducted in a way to retrieve feedback and perceptions from stakeholders in two subsequent phases: one before the demonstration of the W2Power prototype and the other after the pilot test has taken place. This will serve to build a comprehensive and inclusive framework for an integrated planning and delivery of multiuse solutions in the Atlantic basin.

5.1.2. TRAINING EVENTS

Training events will be organised to support knowledge transfer and the project's continuation.

Seminars/Trainings/Workshops will be organised to build the consortium and external organizations' skills on concepts and operations at the multi-use installations. These events will be:

- **Autonomous feeder training:** the required skills to manage certain aspects of the AquaWind prototype such as the autonomous feeder and its maintenance will be trained during the project, with at least **one specific training course** to gain new skill for the technical staff of the consortia and students from the aquaculture operators' degree.
- **Underwater camera training:** AquaWind will incorporate a high resolution 360° motion capacity underwater camera to allow a real time monitoring of fish behaviour, health and welfare and assisting technical staff to take decision about feeding management or specific visits to control fish performance. The utilisation of underwater camera will also need special skills that would be integrated in the training activities foreseen within the project in WP7, task 7.3 "Organisation of events, webinars, workshops and trainings".

5.1.3. WEBINARS

Dedicated webinars will be organized as part of WP7 task 7.3 to reach mainly scientists and innovators on one side and policy makers on the other side. Webinars with policy makers will aim mainly at enabling a favourable legislative and administrative contexts for the deployment of MUP solutions in the Atlantic area and to provide policy makers with figures and estimations on the impact of MUP in different policy areas (environment, marine planning, employment, etc).

There will be **at least 2 webinars for civil society organizations** and **at least 2 webinars for policy makers**.

The format of the webinar will be designed according to the target group. The webinars will be organized in advance including the participation of outstanding speakers and foreseeing space for discussion. Personal invitations will be sent to representatives of the different target groups.

They will be planned so that they can be used **to communicate results/progress** of the project.

5.1.4. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

There will be at least 1 international conference. This will coincide with the end of the project. Thus, this international conference will also be the Final conference where results and main conclusions will be presented. The estimated date for this conference ranges from Month 33 to Month 35 (May 2025 to July 2025).

5.2. ASSISTANCE TO OTHER EVENTS

5.2.1. MAPPING OF EVENTS

A mapping of most relevant events will be performed throughout the project duration. The participation of project partners to other events is of utmost importance in order to exploit synergies and reach a wider number of stakeholders. CE will provide regularly a **list of relevant events** in order for project partners to consider their availability and interest to attend.

In particular, synergies with other EU funded projects will be sought. Events will be mapped to ensure participation of AquaWind to display its exhibition stand, infographics, videos and other project activities. A database will be created and shared in the shared folder with all the events that can be of interest to the consortium.

An initial list of events is proposed below, and it will be updated and expanded on a regular basis:

Blue economy:

- Annual European Maritime Day (EMD)
- Biennial European Wave and Tidal Energy Conference
- Innovazul: II International Meeting of Knowledge and Blue Economy
- International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE)

Aquaculture:

- XVIII Spanish National Congress of Aquaculture
- Aquaculture Europe
- EIT Food's Aquaculture Showcase
- World Aquaculture and Fisheries Conference
- AquaFuture

Wind energy:

- Portugal Renewable Energy Summit
- Wind Europe
- Offshore Energy Exhibition & Conference
- Wind Energy Hamburg

Before and after attending an event, the partners should contact CE indicating the title of the event, place, and date, as well as any supporting documents such as power point presentations, videos and pictures of the event. More details on this are available under D6.1 Consortium Agreement and Management Plan delivered on month 2.

When partners attend an event, but it is not possible to present AquaWind, partners are invited to mention at least the participation of their organization in the project and invite event attendants to visit the [AquaWind project website](#).

5.2.2. NATIONAL / EU EVENTS

The participation of partners in national, European and international events will be promoted, paying special attention to conferences organized in the consortium countries (France, Portugal and Spain). AquaWind will participate to at **least 6 national or EU events** during the course of the project but a higher participation is recommended and expected. For these events partners are expected to **prepare exhibition stands** to promote AquaWind and its results.

6. PRESS OFFICE

The communication actions of the press office include different activities according to the stipulated schedule. To attract the attention of the media, both at regional, national, and international level, the communication actions to be implemented are:

- Drafting and sending press releases and dissemination of newsworthy topics related to the project, the events carried out and the planned communication actions.
- Elaboration of a specific media database, paying special attention to the local and regional media, as well as specialised media such as digital newspapers (INFOPUERTOS, MISPECES, EUROPA AZUL, RUTA PESQUERA) and agencies (EFE, EUROPAPRESS, REUTERS, AFP, LUSA).
- Management of interviews of participants and speakers in radio, press and television. Preparation of own interviews with participants, partners, and collaborators.
- Drafting and sending out press releases for planned project events. Organisation of official and technical press conferences.
- Coordination with the press and protocol offices of public institutions.
- Reinforcement tasks, by means of email marketing and telephone calls, as well as confirmation of attendance at press conferences and reception of press releases.
- Providing the media with permanent download links to the photographic and audiovisual material generated on the different events planned, thanks to the implementation of a dedicated server or through the website.
- Sending infographics, photographic, and audiovisual material, and other project outputs such as the expected handout to the media via corporate e-mail as a complement to the server.
- Informative and logistical assistance for the needs of the media covering the planned events, press conferences and actions.
- Permanent contact with journalists, as well as on-site assistance on their arrival to the onsite events. Provision of an update service for all the information generated.
- Compilation of the impact generated in the media (agencies, written and digital press, radio and television) and preparation of clippings.
- Updating of the media list, registration of new contacts, systematisation and conversion into a database.
- Elaboration and design of a press kit and informative annexes.
- Sending audio-visual material (queues, raw data, totals, etc.) to the media. Translation of press releases if required.
- Preparation of the final communication report.

The generation of content, writing and dissemination of press releases from a dedicated communications office is essential for the international, national, and local media, both general and specialized, to have regular information on the actions to be carried out, covering the whole project, thus maintaining a greater presence in search engines on a regular basis.

7. MANAGEMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

Research data will especially be gathered within work packages 2, 3 and 4. Considering all the information generated in the framework of the project, an efficient knowledge management including the management of Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) should be an integral part of the overall project management structure. Otherwise, arrangements to be considered and established in the CA relevant for IP management should cover aspects such as knowledge management, confidentiality obligations, background, ownership, and transfer of ownership of results, protection and exploitation of results, dissemination, access rights, settlement of disputes, among others. More detailed information about data management might be found on the data management plan.

Since CE manage information generated within the project, especially through its publication on the website, it is vital to highlight some aspects related to IP in the digital age. When setting up a website, it is necessary to be aware of a couple of potential pitfalls and issues related to IP. When looking at our rapidly evolving digital world, questions related to copyright and how to protect content online have been at the forefront of discussions for long. Just because something is online does not mean it is copyright-free. The following list sums up the most important aspects considered when going online on the website:

- Domain name: aquawind.eu was registered successfully, also paying attention to avoiding getting in the way of third party's trademark.
- Most of designs elements used on the website are free of use, such as icons or fonts. Also, CE has the license to freely use original designs from WordPress as well as other designs under Envato Elements of Freepik license certificates as well as other software such as Canva Pro and Adobe Creative Cloud.
- Project trademark and logo is included on the website. Also, other trademarks and logos are included with appropriate authorisation, for example, partners logos.
- Copyright. All original images, videos, and music included on the AquaWind website are protected by copyright. Most licenses provided through paid repositories (Freepik, Envato, Canva).

8. SYNERGIES AND NETWORKING

Task 7.4 “Synergies with other funded projects” deals with establishing relations with other funded projects to foster synergies in knowledge transfer and in exploitation of AquaWind.

8.1. OBJECTIVES AND PRESENTATIONS

To achieve the objectives set for this project and ensure a good dissemination of its results, special attention is given to the creation of **a network of activities**. The partners of the AquaWind project get in touch with companies, entities, higher education institutions and related projects and create synergies with the key actors in the field of aquaculture, offshore wind energy generation and/or multiuse platforms.

These entities either work with marine solutions or study them, for marine solutions development.

In addition, it is also vital to create synergies with European projects and platforms that deal with the abovementioned sectors. Special attention will be given to knowledge transfer between sister projects.

8.2. TARGETS

One of the main target groups of objectives for the creation of networks and synergies consists of other projects related to Horizon Europe or EMFAF projects, as well as other projects financed by the EU. It is about cooperating with project consortia to share the latest information and talk about common issues. EU experts from respective fields of interest will also be contacted to improve and harmonize the general knowledge in these fields and improve its dissemination.

Below there is a table with similar projects that will be contacted for creating synergies and networking:

Table 9. List of possible projects to create synergies with.

Project	Description
MUSICA	The overall Aim of MUSICA is to accelerate the roadmap to commercialisation of its Multi-Use Platform (MUP) and Multi-use of Space (MUS) combination for the small island market, and de-risk for future operators and investors, by validation to TRL7 and providing real plans to move to mass market commercialisation. The MUSICA solution will be a decarbonising one stop shop for small islands, including their marine initiatives (Blue Growth) and ecosystems.
UNITED	This project will provide evidence for the viability of ocean multi-use through the development of five demonstration pilots in the real European marine environment.
FLORA- FLOating RAdar	A project that will develop and demonstrate an industrial-scale prototype of a multi-purpose ocean station with renewable energy generation and operational oceanography capabilities, dubbed the FLORA Ocean Station.
4BIZ	Boosting the Blue Economy in the Black Sea Region by Initiating a Business Collaboration Framework in the field of Fisheries and Aquaculture , Coastal and Maritime Tourism and Maritime Transport
DBAN – Digital Blue economy and innovation Acceleration Network	The project is designed around the concept of establishing a regional blue economy and innovations acceleration network – based ecosystem which supports existing and emerging businesses and business initiatives in the Blue economy sectors, building upon their potential for innovation, circular and bio-based solutions as well as their capacity to contribute to the local/regional sustainable development performance indicators.
PLANASER	The main objective of the project is to consolidate the cultivation of Seriola (<i>S. dumerili</i>) in Spain and position our country as a benchmark in the cultivation of this species through the innovations that are developed, promoting public-private cooperation and the transfer of knowledge to society.

Similarly, a significant target group is the sector working at sea and civil society such as fishermen and citizens. It is crucial to provide results to dissolve doubts and/or concerns they might have regarding both aquaculture and wind-offshore energy.

Cooperation is also established identifying similar projects on the topics that AquaWind is exploring and teaming up with relevant projects for better dissemination and wider audience.

8.3. METHODOLOGY

To carry out a correct control of the contacts for the elaboration of networks, partners should gather their data in the shared excel provided by CE. WP7 leader will also regularly remind partners to share the

network with them. At the same time, the partners that participate in a networking activity are invited to study the possibilities of synergies and collaborations. This can be carried out in various ways, such as:

- Exchange of links on the respective website.
- Exchange of good practices.
- Sharing of public deliverables and other outputs.
- Information on events and activities promoted by AquaWind.
- Invitation of Coordinators/Partners of other projects as speakers at AquaWind events, webinars and/or project meetings.
- Organization of joint events or activities.

After having engaged in a networking activity, partners are kindly asked to fill the shared excel form that will be provided by CE indicating in the relevant column the type of future collaboration which has been suggested.

9. CONTINGENCY PLANS

To be prepared in the case of an impossibility to carry out an in-person event, to avoid unnecessary flights in consideration with the climate crisis and to ensure the maximum attendance of the partners and other stakeholders, an online platform will be used for online meetings. Priority will be given to the use of the zoom platform in the face of possible situations derived from covid-19 and/or other events.

Special consideration will be given to organizing hybrid events to give all partners and stakeholders the possibility of participating both on-site or online.

The chosen software for this will be Zoom, both for informal calls, steering committees, bilateral meetings and webinars.

Below an array of **supporting tools** for the organization of online or hybrid events are provided:

Table 10. Supporting tools for online photo exhibitions

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels
Showcase experience & promote visibility	Instagram
	YOUPIC
	Flickr
	Pinterest
	Behance (by Adobe)
	Vero Social
	Steller Stories

Table 11. Supporting tools for online videos.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels	Optional ideas/notes
Present project results & promote project visibility	YouTube	Creating a series of videos/event (e.g. video days/week)
	Vimeo	
Enhance interaction/participation activities	DailyMotion	Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live videos
	Facebook direct videos	
Exchange views	Instagram direct	

Table 12. Supporting tools for online quiz events.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels	Costs & Participants	Optional ideas/notes
Communicate/transfer project results/insights Promote visibility of the project Encourage interaction	Kahoot	10€/20€/40€ p.m. - 7 days free trial / 20/50/2000	🎥 Videos could be used as a tool/part of an event 🎥 Creating a series of videos/event (e.g. video days/week) 🎥 Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live videos
	Quizizz	Free / -	
	Socrative	free / 99\$ p.a. / 5000 / 10000	
	Typeform	30€/70€	
	Slido	Free / 3 polls per event / 1000 participants	

Table 13. Supporting tools for creative competitions / social media challenges.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Ideas/notes
Showcase experiences Promote visibility of the project Encourage interaction Exchange views	🎥 Participants create input referring to a given topic/task 🎥 Social media as platform / supportive social media wall/liveblog 🎥 Awarding the participants action (e.g. best video, picture, story etc.) 🎥 Creating viral effects / using, chain letters & hashtags 🎥 Creating own input to showcase experiences

Table 14. Supporting tools for creative online workshops.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Ideas/notes
Showcase experiences Promote visibility of the project Promote rural regions & regional projects Exchange views and promote interaction/participation	🎥 Show-Cooking or MasterClass or DIY workshops to gain attention 🎥 Delivering input through introduction/moderation 🎥 Promoting and exchanging specific know-how, products and projects of aquaculture and offshore wind energy. 🎥 Using Facebook direct videos or webinar-tools 🎥 Social media wall/liveblog to promote the event

Table 15. Supporting tools for virtual open-door day/fair.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels	Optional ideas/notes
<p>Communicate/transfer project results/insights Showcase experiences</p> <p>Exchange views/get feedback on project activities/results</p> <p>Exchange best practices/lessons learned</p> <p>Foster networking and interaction</p>	<p>Social media.</p> <p>Direct videos and interaction via Facebook and Instagram</p>	<p> Social media wall/liveblog</p>

Table 16. Supporting tools for virtual summits

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels	Costs	Optional ideas/notes
<p>Communicate/transfer project results/insights Showcase experiences</p> <p>Exchange views/get feedback on project activities/results</p> <p>Exchange best practices/lessons learned</p> <p>Foster networking and interaction</p> <p>Brainstorm on ideas and solutions</p>	<p>Virtual Summits</p> <p>Voxr</p>	<p>97\$ p.m./ 14 days free trial</p> <p>250€ / free up to 20 participants</p>	<p> Liveblog about the summit.</p>

Table 17. Supporting online tools for webinars.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Platform	Costs & Participants	Optional ideas/notes
<p>Communicate/transfer project results/insights</p> <p>Inform on latest policy initiatives/research results</p> <p>Showcase experiences</p> <p>Exchange best practices/lessons learned</p> <p>Get feedback on project activities</p>	GoToMeeting	Professional: 10,75€ (12€)/14,33€ (17€) p.m. / 14 days free / 150/250 participants	<p>Webinars could be used as a tool/part of an event. e.g. webinar days (different webinars and moderators during a period of days)</p> <p>Creating interaction through Q&A rounds, Audience Response Systems (e.g. Polling Tools)</p> <p>Provide extra material, such as transcripts, slides, handouts etc</p>
	GoToWebinar	89€/199€/429€ p.m. / 100/500/1000	
	Zoom	Basic/Pro/Business: free (only 40min.per call)/13,99€/18,99€ p.m / 100/100/300	
	astviewer	38€ p.m. / 30 days free / 100	
	Skype	Free, 50 participants	
	Edudip	34€/69€/139€/244€ p.m. / 30/100/500/1000	
	Adobe Connect	46€/120€/432€/ 34€ p.m. – free trial 25/100/500/1000	
	Webex	free basic version starter/plus/enterprise: 12,85€/17,30€/25,65€50/100/200	
	Jitsi	free (open source) / 200	
	Poll Everywhere	free/25 participants 120\$ p.a./700	
	SurveyMonkey	Free / 40 answers / 39€ p.m / unlimited	
	Slido	Free / 3 polls per event / 1000 participants	
Mentimeter	Free / 2 questions / 5 quizzes per session 9,99€ / unlimited		

Table 18. Supporting tools for online podcasts.

C&D / Engagement objectives	Channels	Cost	Optional ideas / notes
Inform on specific topics, on latest initiatives	Youtube	free + no host needed	Podcasts could be used as a tool/part of an event
	Soundcloud	basic version free + no host needed / Premium: 11€ p.m.	
	iTunes	free / host needed	Creating a series of podcasts/event (e.g. podcast days/week)
	Spotify	free / host needed	
	Host		Creating interaction through reacting on comments and live podcasts
	Podigee	15-29€ p.m. / 30 days free trial	
	Libsyn	5-40\$ p.m.	
	Captivate	19-99\$ p.m. / 7 days free trial	

10. MONITORING AND EVALUATION OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

10.1. MONITORING OF COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Task 7.5 deals with the monitoring and evaluation of D&C activities. These will be monitored to ensure they are properly implemented and concretely support the maximization of the project's expected impacts. Monitoring of the activities allow in fact to assess if the actions planned are carried out properly and on time and to measure their effectiveness. Based on monitoring results, the Plan might be thus **reformulated** to improve the communication and dissemination outreach.

To monitor de project, partners are periodically requested to provide information on the activities carried out (for instance organization of events, publications of news/press releases, etc., presentations at conferences) while CE is in charge of monitoring and reporting on the use of the website, social media, and on the events whose organization is under CE's responsibility. Based on the reports submitted from the partners, CE can formulate recommendations for the future dissemination and communication activities.

Table 19 presents the different monitoring and evaluation activities to be performed, the schedule and the responsibility of partners.

10.2. MONITORING ON PARTNERS' DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

When exploiting synergies and reaching a wider number of stakeholders is key that project partners participate to other events and disseminate project information and results in events such as external events, dissemination publication actions in external websites, newsletters, local radio and conference articles.

A continuous monitoring of the dissemination activities made by project partners is carried out within WP7 tasks. An [excel file](#) keeps records of the press releases, articles, and events, gathering the information based on:

- The partner who carried out the activity.
- The date which the activity took place in.
- Activity outreach.
- Publication source.
- URL link to the activity results or proof.
- Targeted audience.
- In case of an event, the type of event, location, and general information.

Table 19. Monitoring and evaluation activities

Communication activity / tool	Indicators / data	Schedule / frequency of monitoring	Responsible partner
Website and social media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biannual 	CE	
Participation to other events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pictures to be sent the day or the day after for communication purposes 	Project partner	
AquaWind's events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of posts and satisfaction questionnaire to within 1 month following the event 	Partner responsible for the organization of the event	
Dissemination report on communication and dissemination activities performed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biannual 	Project partner	

10.3. EVALUATION OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

In conjunction with the monitoring, an evaluation of the effectiveness of the activities will be performed periodically mainly using a set of indicators of success, including those targets set in the Grant Agreement and reported in the table below. The continuous monitoring will allow CE to assess the evolution and impacts of the dissemination and communication activities and evaluate any corrections or preventive measures to increase the reach-out of WP7 activities.

Table 20. Monitoring and evaluation indicators.

Communication activity / results	Indicator	Target
Events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 80 attendants 	
Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 200 readers per issue 	
Press interviews	N° of interviews	3 per year, 9 total
Press releases	N° of press releases	At least 9 press releases
Project website	Site visits per month	750 site visits
Publications	N° of peer reviewed publications	At least 3 (1 on technical solution, 1 on stakeholder engagement, 1 on environmental impact and carbon reduction)
Social media	Followers (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, YouTube)	1000 followers
Videos	N° of videos produced	At least 3 videos (1 animated, 1 demonstration of technology, 1 storytelling)
Webinars	N° of webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2 for policy makers

11. PROGRESS ON DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

This section provides a brief overview of the main dissemination and communication activities carried out up to the presentation of this document.

11.1.1. ROLL UP

Four versions have been developed during the first two months of the project. The first three ones were edited by the Coordinator's and CE's feedback. During the Kick-off meeting the consortium had the chance to view the roll up and give feedback. The fourth and final version was developed thanks to their comments. The roll up could be edited again if needed.

Figure 3. Roll-up.

The roll up is 85cm x 200cm and has been distributed to partners to be utilized in the dissemination activities.

11.1.2. LEAFLET

The leaflet was built in the first months of the project. It consists of AquaWind objectives, expected outcomes, project and partners as well as information on the social media.

Figure 4. Leaflet.

11.1.3. WEBSITE

The project website <https://aquawind.eu/> has been recently created. The structure of the website is as follows:

- 🌐 Home:
 - Main introductory picture. This picture will be updated once the prototype is put on the water.
 - Brief description of the project.
 - Newsletter box to subscribe to the newsletter.

Figure 5. Website "Home".

 About. Main information regarding the project.

Figure 6. Website: About.

- Work Packages. Inside the project tab you can find all Work packages explained with pictures and results updates.

Figure 7. Website: work packages.

- Consortium. The entire consortium with each partner's role at the project.

Figure 8. Website: Consortium.

- Networking / Other sister projects tab under "about". This section gives useful information regarding other sister projects and other resources.

Sister projects

<p>FLORA- Floating Radar</p> <p>Link:</p> <p>A project that will develop and demonstrate an industrial-scale prototype of a multi-purpose ocean station with renewable...</p>		
<p>PLANASER</p> <p>Link: https://planaser.es</p> <p>The main objective of the project is to consolidate the cultivation of Seriola (S. dumerli) in Spain and position our country...</p>		

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Copyright © 2022 Aquawind
Developed by Consulta Europa S.L.

Figure 9. Networking tab.

Project.

- Main description of the project with its objectives.
- Communication materials and public deliverables called “Project Results”.

Project

The aim of AquaWind is to perform a demonstration test of a multi-use (MU) integrated and co-located solution. This would consist of joining an existing marine renewable energy production, the W2Power prototype, with an innovative aquaculture solution. The aquaculture prototype will include a tailor-made design fish cage with novel net materials, a high level of digitalization and species diversification. Whereas the W2Power prototype will consist of floating wind technology.

For the first time, this project performs MU test trials joining marine energy production with live fish aquaculture in the Atlantic region. AquaWind joins the efforts of a multidisciplinary stakeholders' consortia including R&D centres, companies, regional authorities, and a maritime cluster from three EU member states (ES, FR, PT) in the Atlantic basin. In addition to that, AquaWind will involve a wide network of stakeholders throughout all the project phases to ensure social acceptance. The project will provide a route map for regulatory and legal issues that need to be addressed for real implementation of MU projects, taking advantage of and facilitating interaction with previous and ongoing EU-funded projects.

AquaWind will also demonstrate how the joint activity can be digitised to be remotely operated in the same maritime space with different fish species (sparus aurata as control and seriola dumerilii as novel) and how one activity might affect the other, before going one step further to become the new W2Power prototype a commercial solution. Thus, AquaWind will provide real data to demonstrate the economic, environmental, and social sustainability of the MU proposal: providing a business model case and exploitation plan to evaluate the cost reduction of commissioning, maintenance and operation of the combined activity including the evolution of the prototype. Also, it will provide real data of the monitoring campaign to evaluate the environmental impact in the surrounding maritime space by measuring the CO₂ footprint.

The project fully responds to the objectives to support the development and uptake of MU between marine renewable energies and other blue economy activities (aquaculture) and contribute to the Atlantic Maritime Strategy priority to develop marine renewable energy and the sustainable expansion of the Blue Economy (BE) in the Atlantic Basin. In this regard, AquaWind focuses on specific solutions suggested for MU projects that were specifically encouraged by the European Commission in its guidelines for a more sustainable and competitive EU aquaculture for 2021 to 2030.

Figure 10. Website: Project description under “Project” tab.

- Results

Communication & dissemination

Figure 11. Website: Project tab: Results.

- Gallery. A tab under “project” shows the images taken during the project:

Figure 12. Website: gallery

 News. Latest project news as well as news from other relevant projects, initiatives, and organizations in the field:

Figure 13. Website: News & social media feed.

- AquaWind in the News:

Figure 14. Website: AquaWind in the News.

- 🌊 Events. Organized or assisted by AquaWind, events of interest

March 2023

28 March 2023
30 March 2023

Aquafuture
Aquafuture, II International Show of the Aquaculture Industry --
28-30 marzo 2023 This meeting is designed as ...

All Day

View Details >

November 2022

29 November 2022
02 December 2022

Innovazul
InnovAzul is the meeting space for professionals from the Blue
Economy sectors to promote innovation and ...

All Day

INTERNACIONAL DE CONOCIMIENTO Y ECONOMÍA
NAL MEETING OF KNOWLEDGE AND BLUE ECONOMY

INTERNATIONAL B2B MEETINGS
November 29th - December 1st 2022, CAIBO

View Details >

21 November 2022
24 November 2022

**Spanish National Congress of
Aquaculture**
Under the slogan "Aquaculture: seas and rivers of opportunities"
of the XVIII National Aquaculture Congress, AquaWind ...

All Day

View Details >

Figure 15. Website: Events.

 Contact. Contact information.

Figure 16. Website: Contact form.

This website will be continuously updated with new content.

11.1.4. SOCIAL MEDIA

AquaWind can be followed on Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn. These accounts have just been created and will be updated regularly during the duration of the project with information on project results, partners, events organized, interviews, other relevant project's events, results and information. To this date (November 2022) these are the accounts and their posts and followers:

- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/aquawind.eu>
 - User: @aquawind.eu
 - Followers: 10
 - Posts: 5
- Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/aquawind/>
 - User: @aquawind_
 - Followers: 59
 - Posts: 3
- Twitter: <https://twitter.com/AquawindP>
 - User: @aquawindP
 - Followers: 9
 - Posts: 5
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/aquawind-project-9b321b247/>
 - User: AquaWind Project
 - Followers: 69
 - Posts: 7

A YouTube account (user: AquaWind) has also been created that will serve as a repository for the audiovisual material.

HASHTAGS

The hashtags that have been defined by CE and by suggestions of the PO are:

#AquaWind #aquaculture #offshore #windenergy #multiplesolution #CINEA #multiuse
#renewableenergy #W2Power #prototype #floatingwindtechnology #Atlanticregion #EMFAF

11.1.5. EVENTS

At this stage, only the Kick-off meeting has been organized and some partners (EnerOcean, CMC, ULPGC) have already attended three events: Offshore wind energy in the Canary Islands Day, the International Ocean Conference on Ocean Energy (ICOE) and the XVIII Spanish National Aquaculture Congress.

During task 7.5 Monitoring and evaluation of D&C activities all the events will be tracked and be detailed under deliverables 7.5, 7.6 & 7.7, "Reports on D&C activities". These deliverables are due months 12, 24 & 36 which are August 2023, August 2024 & August 2025.

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Co-funded by
the European Union